

A Comparative Study of Emotional Intelligence among B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students

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ABSTRACT

Emotional intelligence is the ability to identify, understand, manage and use emotions in positive ways to relieve from stress, defuse conflict, communicate effectively, empathize with others and overcome challenges. The purpose research attempted to study the comparative Study of Emotional Intelligence among B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students. **Objectives-** 1) To examine the B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with Emotional Intelligence on dimension self-awareness, Empathy, Emotional stability, self-motive managing relations, Integrity, Self-development. Value orientation, Commitment and Altruistic behavior. **Hypotheses:** 1) There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students Emotional Intelligence on dimension self-awareness, Empathy, Emotional stability, self-motive managing relations, Integrity, Self-development. Value orientation, Commitment and Altruistic behavior. **Methodology. Sample:** Total sample of present study 120, in which 40 were B.A. Students, 40 were B. Com. Students and 40 B.Sc. college students. Non-Probability Quota Sampling was used. The subject selected in this sample was age group of 18-21 year. **Research Design:** In the present study a balanced 3x2x2 factorial design will be used. **Variables-** The independent variables are Faculty and Dependent variables are Emotional Intelligence. **Research Tools-** Emotional Intelligence scale by Hyde, Pethe, Dhor and Dhar(2002). **Statistical Treatment:** Mean, SD and 'F' values used. **Conclusions-** 1) B.Com. College Students High Self-awareness than B.A. and B.Sc. College Students. 2) No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Empathy, Self-Motivation, Managing Relations, Integrity, Commitment, Emotional Stability and Altruistic Behavior. 3) B.Sc. College Students High Self-development, Value orientation and Emotional Intelligence than B.A. and B.Com College Students.

Key words: *Self-awareness, Empathy, Self-Motivation, Managing Relations, Integrity, Self-development, Value orientation, Commitment, Emotional Stability, Altruistic Behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence is more important than one's intelligence in attaining success in lives and careers. As individuals, our successes in life as well as profession depend on our ability to read other people's signals and react appropriately.

Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotions. It is the capacity that one possesses or abstains over a period of time to generate optimum results in relationship with oneself and others. It is also the ability to monitor one's own and others feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive accurately, apprise and express emotions; the ability to access and /or generate feelings when they facilitate thoughts; the ability to understand emotions and emotional knowledge; the ability to regulate emotions to promote educational and intellectual growth.

Emotional intelligence can be expressed as feelings, for example the need to feel accepted, respected and important

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while all humans share these needs, each differ in the strength of need, just as some of us need more water, more food, more sleep. One person may need more freedom and independence; another may need more security and social connections. Knowing about one's Emotional Intelligence in terms of an Emotion Quotient has wide educational and social implications for the welfare of the individual and the society. This fact has now been recognized and given practical shape and implication all around the globe. A person's Emotional Intelligence helps him much in all spheres of life through its various constituents or components the achievement of the end results in terms of better handling of mutual relationships is quite essential and significant in his life. It can only be possible through his potential of Emotional Intelligence and its proper development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mohd. Moshahid, (2017) this study revealed that there is no significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence of management and engineering students. There is significant difference between the level of emotional

intelligence of management and engineering male students. There is no significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence of management and engineering female students. The study also found that there is significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence of management male and female students. However, there is no significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence of engineering male and female students.

Labhane and Baviskar (2015) this study found that there is significant difference in emotional intelligence between the arts and science faculty students. Science faculty students have highest emotional intelligence than arts faculty students.

Kavita Mittal, (2017) this study found that Science students show higher general intelligence than the arts students.

Sinha's (1967) study showed arts and science groups significantly discriminated (beyond 0.01 level) on the variable of intelligence, science students scored significantly higher on the intelligence test than the students of arts.

Chatterji (1983) in his study found science students the most intelligent and the arts students the least.

Dhammi and Choubey (2014) found that science and humanities group students, graduate and post graduate students showed no significant difference in their general intelligence.

Statement problem of the Study

“A comparative Study of Emotional Intelligence among B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students”

Objective of the study

- To examine the B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students of Emotional Intelligence Factor on dimension self-

awareness, Empathy, Emotional stability, self-motive managing relations, Integrity, Self-development. Value orientation, Commitment and Altruistic behavior.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on self-awareness.
2. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Empathy.
3. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Emotional stability.
4. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on self-motives.
5. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on managing relations.
6. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Integrity.
7. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Self-development.
8. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Value orientation.
9. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Commitment.
10. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Altruistic behavior.
11. There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Emotional Intelligence.

METHODS

Sample

For the present study 120 samples was selected from Aurangabad district (MS). Non-Probability Quota Sampling was used. The subject selected in this sample was age group of 18-21 year. The sample of present study was shows as below.

Gender		Faculty						Total
		Arts		Commerce		Science		
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Area of Residence	Urban	10	10	10	10	10	10	60
	Rural	10	10	10	0	10	10	60
Total		20	20	20	20	20	20	120

Research Design

3 x 2 x2 Factorial research design used

B		A					
		A1		A2		A3	
		B1	B2	B1	B2	B1	B2
C	C1	A1,B1,C1	A1,B2,C1	A2,B1,C1	A2,B2,C1	A3,B1,C1	A3,B2,C1
	C2	A1,B1,C2	A1,B2,C2	A2,B1,C2	A2,B2,C2	A3,B1,C2	A3,B2,C2

- A. Faculty A1- B.A. Students A2- B.Com Students A3- B.Sc. Students
- B. Gender **B1**- Male Students **B2**- Female Students
- C. Area of Residence **C1**- Urban Students **C2**- Rural Students

Variables of the Study

Type of variable	Variable	Sub. Factor	Name of variable
Independent Variables	Faculty	03	1. B.A, College Students 2. B. Com College Students 3. B. Sc. College Students
Dependent variables	Emotional Intelligence	10	1. .Self-awareness 2. Empathy 3. Self- Motivation 4. Emotional stability 5. Managing Relations 6. Integrity 7. Self- development 8. Value orientation 9. Commitment 10. Altruistic Behavior

Research Tools

Aspect	Name of the Test	Author	Sub Factor	
Emotional Intelligence	Emotional Intelligence scale (2002)	Anukool Hyde. Sanjot Pethe. Upinder Dhar	1. Self-awareness	Item- 50
			2. Empathy	Scoring- 1) Strongly disagree, 2) Disagree, 3) Neutral, 4) Agree, 5) strongly agree
			3. Self- Motivation	Reliability - 0.88
			4. Emotional stability	Validity - 0.93
			5. Managing Relations	
			6. Integrity	
			7. Self- development	
			8. Value orientation	
			9. Commitment	
			10. Altruistic Behavior	

PROCEDURES OF DATA COLLECTION:-

The primary information was gathered by giving personal information from to each student. The students were called in a small group of 20 to 25 students. The students provided the Emotional Intelligence scale. Data were obtained by using particular scoring particular scoring palter standardized for each scale.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

Mean, S.D and ANOVA were College Students to analyses the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Hypothesis-01: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Self-awareness.

Table No.01

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Self-awareness	B.A. College Students	13.02	2.27	40	117	8.68	0.01
	B.Com. College Students	14.65	1.56	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	14.12	2.52	40			

Graph No. 01

Results shown in Table No. 01 and Graph No. 01 indicated that mean and SD values of Self-awareness obtained were 13.02 ± 2.27 by the B.A. College Students, were 14.65 ± 1.56 by the B.Com. College Students and 14.12 ± 2.52 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Self-awareness is observed 8.68 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of significance, 1st hypothesis is reject because table value less than calculated value. It means that B.Com. College Students High Self-awareness than B.A. and B.Sc. College Students.

Hypothesis-02: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Empathy.

Table No.02

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Empathy	B.A. College Students	16.05	3.14	40	117	3.12	NS
	B.Com. College Students	17.32	3.50	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	17.05	3.65	40			

Graph No. 02

Results shown in Table No. 02 and Graph No. 02 indicated that mean and SD values of Empathy obtained were 16.05 ± 3.14 by the B.A. College Students, were 17.32 ± 3.50 by the B.Com. College Students and 17.05 ± 3.65 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Empathy is observed 3.12 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 2nd hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Empathy.

Hypothesis-03: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Self-Motivation.

Table No.03

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Self-Motivation	B.A. College Students	18.90	3.91	40	117	1.60	NS
	B.Com. College Students	19.25	3.43	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	19.80	3.22	40			

Graph No. 03

Results shown in Table No. 03 and Graph No. 03 indicated that mean and SD values of Self-Motivation obtained were 18.90 ± 3.91 by the B.A. College Students, were 19.25 ± 3.43 by the B.Com. College Students and 19.80 ± 3.22 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Self-Motivation is observed 1.60 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 3th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Self-Motivation.

Hypothesis-04: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Managing Relations.

Table No.04

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Managing Relations	B.A. College Students	12.82	3.55	40	117	0.260	NS
	B.Com. College Students	13.00	2.98	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	13.15	2.64	40			

Graph No. 04

Results shown in Table No. 04 and Graph No. 04 indicated that mean and SD values of Managing Relations obtained were 12.82 ± 3.55 by the B.A. College Students, were 13.00 ± 2.98 by the B.Com. College Students and 13.15 ± 2.64 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Managing Relations is observed 0.260 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 4th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Managing Relations.

Hypothesis-05: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Integrity.

Table No.05

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Integrity	B.A. College Students	11.72	3.81	40	117	3.81	NS
	B.Com. College Students	11.75	3.95	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	12.90	2.81	40			

Graph No. 05

Results shown in Table No. 05 and Graph No. 05 indicated that mean and SD values of Integrity obtained were 11.72 ± 3.81 by the B.A. College Students, were 11.75 ± 3.95 by the B.Com. College Students and 12.90 ± 2.81 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Integrity is observed 3.81 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is $0.01 = 3.94$ and at $0.05 = 6.90$ levels of not significance, 5th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Integrity.

Hypothesis-06: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Self-development.

Table No.06

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Self-development	B.A. College Students	8.57	2.74	40	117	10.40	0.01
	B.Com. College Students	10.02	3.11	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	10.27	2.07	40			

Graph No. 06

Results shown in Table No. 06 and Graph No. 06 indicated that mean and SD values of Self-development obtained were 8.57 ± 2.74 by the B.A. College Students, were 10.02 ± 3.11 by the B.Com. College Students and 10.27 ± 2.07 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Self-development is observed 10.40 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is $0.01 = 3.94$ and at $0.05 = 6.90$ levels of significance, 6th hypothesis is rejected because table value less than calculated value. It means that B.Sc. College Students High Self-development than B.A. and B.Com College Students.

Hypothesis-07: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Value orientation.

Table No.07

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Value orientation	B.A. College Students	5.35	1.56	40	117	4.58	0.05
	B.Com. College Students	6.05	1.76	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	6.50	1.39	40			

Graph No. 07

Results shown in Table No. 07 and Graph No. 07 indicated that mean and SD values of Value orientation obtained were 5.35 ± 1.56 by the B.A. College Students, were 6.05 ± 1.76 by the B.Com. College Students and 6.50 ± 1.39 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Value orientation is observed 4.58 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of significance, 7th hypothesis is reject because table value less than calculated value. It means that B.Sc. College Students High Value orientation than B.A. and B.Com College Students.

Hypothesis-08: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Commitment.

Table No.08

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Commitment	B.A. College Students	6.07	1.68	40	117	1.14	NS
	B.Com. College Students	6.45	1.76	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	6.37	1.47	40			

Graph No. 08

Results shown in Table No. 08 and Graph No. 08 indicated that mean and SD values of Commitment obtained were 6.07 ± 1.68 by the B.A. College Students, were 6.45 ± 1.76 by the B.Com. College Students and 6.37 ± 1.47 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Commitment is observed 1.14 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 8th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Commitment.

Hypothesis-09: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Emotional Stability.

Table No.09

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Emotional Stability	B.A. College Students	5.75	1.66	40	117	2.85	NS
	B.Com. College Students	6.30	1.66	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	6.25	1.33	40			

Graph No. 09

Results shown in Table No. 09 and Graph No. 09 indicated that mean and SD values of Emotional Stability obtained were 5.75 ± 1.66 by the B.A. College Students, were 6.30 ± 1.66 by the B.Com. College Students and 6.25 ± 1.33 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Emotional Stability is observed 2.85 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 9th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Emotional Stability.

Hypothesis-10: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students with dimension Emotional Intelligence on Altruistic Behavior.

Table No.10

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Altruistic Behavior	B.A. College Students	6.25	1.29	40	117	1.64	NS
	B.Com. College Students	6.05	1.26	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	6.85	1.53	40			

Graph No. 10

Results shown in Table No. 10 and Graph No. 10 indicated that mean and SD values of Altruistic Behavior obtained were 6.25 ± 1.29 by the B.A. College Students, were 6.05 ± 1.26 by the B.Com. College Students and 6.85 ± 1.53 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Altruistic Behavior is observed 1.14 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is 0.01 = 1.64 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels of not significance, 10th hypothesis is Accepted because table value High than calculated value. It means that no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Altruistic Behavior.

Hypothesis-11: There is no significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Emotional Intelligence.

Table No.11

Factor	Faculty	Mean	SD	N	DF	F Value	Sign.
Emotional Intelligence	B.A. College Students	104.25	17.75	40	117	11.17	0.01
	B.Com. College Students	110.72	18.80	40			
	B.Sc. College Students	112.25	15.70	40			

Graph No. 11

Results shown in Table No. 11 and Graph No. 11 indicated that mean and SD values of Emotional Intelligence obtained were 104.25 ± 17.75 by the B.A. College Students, were 110.72 ± 18.80 by the B.Com. College Students and 112.25 ± 15.70 by B.Sc. College Students. The F value between B.A., B.Com. And B.Sc. College Students on Emotional Intelligence is observed 3711.17 at 117 degree of freedom. The table value of F value is $0.01 = 3.94$ and at $0.05 = 6.90$ levels of significance, this hypothesis is reject because table value less than calculated value. It means that B.Sc. College Students High Emotional Intelligence than B.A. and B.Com College Students.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The finding of the study is based on only 120 sample use.
2. The sample was restricted to Aurangabad city Dist. in Maharashtra.
3. The study was restricted to only arts, Commence and Science college students only.
4. The study was restricted students are only 18-21 years only.
5. The study was restricted students are urban and rural area students.

CONCLUSIONS

1. B.Com. College Students High Self-awareness than B.A. and B.Sc. College Students.
2. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Empathy.
3. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Self-Motivation.
4. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Managing Relations.
5. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Integrity.
6. B.Sc. College Students High Self-development than B.A. and B.Com College Students.
7. B.Sc. College Students High Value orientation than B.A. and B.Com College Students.
8. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Commitment.
9. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Emotional Stability.
10. No significant difference between B.A, B. Com and B. Sc. College Students on Altruistic Behavior.
11. B.Sc. College Students High Emotional Intelligence than B.A. and B.Com College Students.

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